

Growth, Vibrational, Optical, Mechanical and Dielectrical studies of EDTA Doped Cupric Sulphate-Zinc Chloride Crystals

J. Aarthi,¹ S. Gowri,^{2,*} S.Sujatha,³ R. Nirmal Kumar,³ and R. Thiyagarajan³

¹ Department of Physics, Seethalakshmi Ramaswami College, Trichy

² Department of Physics, Cauvery College for women, Trichy

³ PG and Research Department of Physics, Srimad Andavan Arts & Science College, Trichy

* Corresponding Author: gow.1976@gmail.com (90435 01140)

Abstract

The Zn is a conventional semiconducting material, whereas Cu is a common metal, and both are having the centro-symmetry structure independently. The Ethylene Diamine Tetra Acetic acid (EDTA) is a hexa dentate ligand, and it binds with central metal ions through the four oxygen and two nitrogen atoms [1]. Hence, the doping of EDTA with Zn and Cu individually can provide NLO property to these elements. Here, crystals of Ethylene Diamine Tetra Acetic acid (EDTA) doped Cupric Sulphate Zinc chloride (Cu-Zn) was grown by Slow Evaporation Solution Technique from an aqueous solution. Powder X-ray diffraction was performed to assess the crystalline nature. Structural analysis by the functional groups was investigated using FT-IR spectroscopy, and the shifting of frequency represents the coordination of EDTA in the grown crystal [2]. Fluorescence Spectra was recorded to explore its emission properties. Mechanical behavior was analyzed using the Vickers microhardness test. The variation of microhardness number with applied load explains the RISE behavior of the grown crystal. Using Wooster's empirical relation the elastic stiffness constant (C_{11}) was calculated from the Vickers hardness values at different loads. The impedance analysis was performed to characterize the electrical properties as a function of frequency to understand their relaxation and conduction mechanism. These studies were confirmed the enhancement of all these physical properties of Cu-Zn by doping of EDTA.

Keywords: Crystal growth, SEST, Powder XRD, FTIR, Mechanical strength.

Reference

[1] Jeffery GH, et al., Vogul's text book of Quantitativechemical Analysis (ELIBS). Addison Wesley Longman Limited. UK; 1989.

[2] P. Manimekalai, et al., International Research Journal of Pure & Applied Chemistry, 3(4): 391-403, 2013.